

Enriched in RS	p
X vs 3	0.1131
X vs 6	0.4052
X vs 14	0.1271

Enriched in RS	p
Y vs 16	<.0001
Y vs 18	<.0001

RS specific	p
X vs 3	<.0001
X vs 6	<.0001
X vs 14	0.0059

RS specific	p
Y vs 16	0.0401
Y vs 18	0.0028